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Evolution and Taxonomy of Portfolio Optimization: Traditional Theories vs. Neural Network Innovations

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Abstract

This paper examines the evolution of portfolio theory, beginning with the foundational mean-variance framework introduced by Markowitz, and explores advancements in computational methods, particularly artificial neural networks (ANNs), for addressing modern portfolio optimization challenges. While traditional models like the efficient frontier remain pivotal, they often struggle with real-world constraints such as dynamic data interactions, non-linear relationships, and high-dimensional datasets. Through a comparative analysis, we demonstrate how machine learning techniques—especially Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and hybrid deep learning architectures—overcome these limitations by enabling robust predictions of asset returns and optimal weight allocation. Empirical evidence from reviewed studies highlights that neural network models significantly outperform classical approaches in terms of Sharpe ratios, risk-adjusted returns, and adaptability to complex financial environments. The study underscores the necessity of integrating traditional financial theories with advanced machine learning to enhance portfolio diversification, risk management, and return optimization. This synthesis not only clarifies the strengths and weaknesses of existing models but also provides a roadmap for future research in adaptive, data-driven portfolio strategies.

Keywords: Portfolio optimization, Markowitz model, efficient frontier, neural networks, LSTM, risk-return tradeoff, machine learning in finance.

JEL classification: G11, G17.

1. Introduction

An investor's portfolio can be explained as a group of investment assets that are combined for proper risk and proper return. An investment is often made in real assets like property plant and equipment, real estate, and/or in financial assets like stocks and bonds. A country's investment rate features a direct impact on its economic growth as a higher rate of investment results in a larger stock of physical capital, which successfully increases labor productivity and potential GDP (Bodie, Kane and Marcus, 2013). Financial markets allow funds to transfer from one group to another that can make the best use of them (Mishkin and Eakins, 2015). Businesses and governments often need to raise capital to invest in real assets to expand their operations and generate more income. They must raise the capital needed in the financial markets by issuing securities and selling them to individuals and groups with a surplus of funds (Jones, 2010). The incomes generated by real assets that are financed by the issuance of these securities afford the investors with their requisite return (Bodie, Kane and

Marcus, 2013). People are risk-averse when the mutual goal of all investors is either to achieve a high return when a level of risk is stated or to attain a minimum risk level for a predetermined return (Jones, 2010), which Harry Markowitz (1952, 1959), the father of the modern portfolio, highlighted in his paper on portfolio selection (1952). Construction of an optimal portfolio requires prediction for stocks' returns for stock selection and then determining the optimal structure of the selected portfolio (Holgersson, Karlsson and Stephan, 2020). Problems of financial modeling – such as estimation of stock returns and portfolio creation – often include vast data sets and dynamic data interactions that are currently difficult or impossible to determine in a complete economic model. Technically problems in data collections for financial predictions such as the difficulty in dealing with a wide variety of data sources, the complexity and non-linearity among the relevant data collected which are not well defined by financial economic theory conduce further research on identifying predictive models in which many are subject to over-fitting and poor predictive out-of-sample performance. What is really needed is a model that can learn such complex data input features and leads to better predictions of the target output variables (portfolio return, optimal portfolio structure) (Heaton, Polson and Witte, 2016).

2. Fundamentals and Evolution of Portfolio Theory

Much academic debate has been positioned around investment diversification and portfolio risk. One of the original theories was proposed by Williams who understood that the expected cash flows of a stock (dividends) or a bond (interest payments and principal) are not definite. So, security valuation and probabilities should be applied to dissimilar possible security values and the means of those values used as the security value. He told readers that risk can be practically eliminated by investing in ample numbers of securities. Markowitz (1952, 1959, 1962) introduced the mean-variance model where the expected (mean) return and the variance of return (risk) of the portfolio were considered parameters for portfolio selection. “The expected (mean) return on a portfolio is the weighted average of the probable returns on its individual securities, whereas the variance of return on the portfolio is a function of three factors: the variances, the covariances amidst securities and their weights in the portfolio” (Markowitz, 1999). As the number of n securities increases in a portfolio the portfolio risk falls, but it is not reduced to zero. Thus, market risk cannot be eliminated even with extensive diversification. This efficient frontier theory is the most imperative investment strategies for any degree of expected mean returns. However, it fails to eradicate the portfolio exposure to market risk even with diversification rooted in the correlation between securities. It is also unable to consider real-world investment constraints such as trade limits, amount of funds invested in the portfolio, etc. as well as cardinality limitations to guarantee investment with respect to a specific number of various assets, and also does not include limits on the funds invested in each asset (Deng, Lin and Lo, 2012).

Similarly, Roy suggested portfolio selection derived from the mean-variance of the portfolio as a whole by selecting a portfolio that maximizes portfolio $(E-d)/\sigma$, where:

- E is the predicted (mean) return,
- d is a fixed catastrophic return and
- σ is the standard deviation of return.

Roy's portfolio variance formula is similar to that of Markowitz, which includes the covariances of securities returns. However, while Markowitz wanted non-negative investments, Roy allowed positive/negative investments. Moreover, Markowitz permitted the selection of a preferred portfolio derived from the efficient frontier, Roy advocated selecting a particular portfolio (Markowitz, 1999).

Tobin (1958) established the required conditions to warrant an optimal mean variance theory either by investor's utility function or assets' distribution of returns (Elton and Gruber, 1997). Tobin focused on investing in monetary assets like cash, since they are highly marketable, liquid, and very secure, thus showing mean-variance-efficiency. Tobin's work resulted in what is called the Tobin Separation Theorem. Tobin (1958) and Sharpe (1967) proposed a model for portfolio selection that consists of a combination of risky and a risk-free asset i.e. cash. If the assets were monetary, the risk would be of market and not of a default. There had to be a level of non-negativity in the holdings and it was also not possible to borrow. More importantly, Sharpe believed that as investors invest (lend/borrow) at risk-free rate, one specific grouping of unsafe assets plus lending or borrowing would compose all efficient portfolios. The two works vary in terms of Sharpe's assumption which stated that his model extended to the securities and “capital

assets” in totality, while Tobin was of the opinion that the model he proposed was only applicable to "monetary assets” (Markowitz, 1999). Hicks (1962), without acknowledging Tobin (1952), introduced a comparable model that was a general formula based on portfolio variance that rather than co-variances, was written in terms of correlations. He also examined the efficient frontier after the point where cash holding is equal to zero and also observed that as we move out beside the frontier, facing increasing risk and return, securities quit the efficient portfolio. However, Hicks (1935) was not of the opinion to classify standard deviation nor other specific dispersion measures as a risk for analysis; thus, he was unable to present a risk-related formula for individual assets on the portfolio. He did not create a dissimilarity among efficient and inefficient portfolios, include a drawing for an efficient frontier, or put forth a hypothesis stating that all efficient portfolios bearing cash portray similar quantities with respect to risky assets (Markowitz, 1999). Leavens highlighted the advantages of diversification on the basis of independent risks. Marschak (1938), attempted to build an ordinal theory of selection under uncertainty and used indifference curves in the mean – variance arena to describe preferences for investments. Like Hicks, he tried to coin a superior explanation of money by combining General Price Theory to it. Marschak noted that people seem to like meaner and less standard deviation. He noticed that people prefer 'long odds' (i.e., high positive skewness of yields.”, where each yield was subject to only two parameters, the statistical expectation ('lucrative-ness') as well as the variance coefficient ('risk') (Markowitz, 1999). Marschak’s cannot be seen as a move towards portfolio theory (beyond Hicks 1935) for it does not consider portfolios.

Further to the aforementioned theories, a number of researchers suggested substitutional portfolio theories containing additional moments like skewness or those suitable for more practical explanations of return distribution. Nonetheless, mean variance theory remains the foundation of modern portfolio analysis for two reasons: First, it imposes big data conditions on the investor itself. Secondly, its potential consequences are quite well-developed and highly intuitive. Finally, professionals deduced that there is a need to understand the theory behind correlations, means and variances to recognize the effect of a security being added to a portfolio (Elton and Gruber, 1997).

Table 1: A Comparative Table: Portfolio Theories Features

Models	Elimination of Risk	Parameters	Investments
Markowitz, 1952	Partial	Mean-Variance	Non-negative
Roy (1952)	Partial	Mean-Variance	Positive-negative
Tobin (1958)	Partial	Mean-Variance	Positive-negative
Sharpe 1967	Partial	Mean-Variance	Positive-negative
Hicks (1935, 1962)	Partial	Mean-Variance	Positive-negative
Marschak (1938)	Complete	Mean-Variance	Non-negative
Williams (1938)	Complete	Mean-Variance	Non-negative

In order to understand the Markowitz Portfolio theory, several formulas have to be presented:

Expected Return on Portfolio (p) (Jones, 2010):

$$E(R_p) = \sum_{i=1}^n W_i E(R_i) \tag{1}$$

Where,

$E(R_p)$: portfolio expected (mean) return

W_i : weight of the i th security in portfolio P ; the amount of funds invested over the value of the portfolio.

$$\sum w_i = 1.0$$

$E(R_i)$: expected return on the i th security

n : number of various securities in portfolio P

Variance of Return for a 2 risky asset portfolio: (the standard deviation is the portfolio risk measure) (Jones, 2010)

$$\sigma_p^2 = W_1^2 \sigma_1^2 + W_2^2 \sigma_2^2 + 2(W_1)(W_2)(\rho_{1,2}) \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \tag{2}$$

Figure 1 shows how portfolio risk and return vary with different weighted combinations of securities in the portfolio (Bodie, Kane and Marcus, 2013).

Figure 1: The attainable set with risky assets (Bodie, Kane and Marcus, 2013)

Figure 2 illustrates the efficient frontier that constitutes the set of all efficient portfolios an investor should choose from the minimum variance portfolio (MVP) and above according to his return-risk preferences (Jones, 2010).

Figure 2: The efficient frontier (Bodie, Kane and Marcus, 2013)

Figure 3 shows how the degree of “correlation coefficient” ($-1.0 < \rho < +1.0$) between securities changes the form of the opportunity set; The smaller the correlation, the greater the risk reduction potential (Bodie, Kane and Marcus, 2013).

Figure 3: The opportunity sets with different correlation coefficients (Bodie, Kane and Marcus, 2013)

Figure 4 illustrates the effect of diversification on portfolio risk. (Bodie, Kane and Marcus, 2013).

Figure 4: Portfolio risk shown as a function of the number of securities in the portfolio (Bodie, Kane and Marcus, 2013)

3. Artificial Neural Networks- A New Portfolio Selection Model

The past decade has seen machine learning (ML) techniques, in particular deep learning (DL) make great progress. The DL deals with diverse architectures of deep neural networks that have outperformed traditional methods including other ML techniques for various tasks. This progress has been engendered by both advancements in computational power and availability of large datasets. The latter is absolutely essential for training and validation of a deep network. The amount of data generated in stock trading makes it ideal for application of DL methods. However, the nature of this data comes with its own challenges. In this section, we will take a look at these challenges and important recent developments.

3.1. Challenges in Portfolio Optimization

For investment firms and investors, stock selection and portfolio management are essential (Yang, Liu and Wu, 2018). Portfolio management is a decision-making mechanism where a fund amount is distributed to different financial assets and the allocation weight is continuously adjusted to optimize returns and minimize risk (Markowitz, 1999). There are two problems surrounding portfolio creation. The first is to choose higher-income assets and the other is to assess the value composition of assets in the portfolio in order to achieve the target of maximizing potential returns with minimal risk. Construction of an optimal portfolio requires prediction for stocks' returns for stock selection and then determining the optimal structure of the selected portfolio. The problem of how to estimate portfolio weights so as to

minimize the variance in portfolio returns was given considerable attention in the literature, and several methods were proposed. However, some of the properties of these estimators remain unknown and thus, many of their relative strengths and weaknesses are difficult for users to determine (Holgerson, Karlsson and Stephan, 2020).

Financial prediction problems – such as estimation of stock returns and portfolio creation – often include vast data sets and dynamic data interactions that are currently difficult or impossible to determine in a complete economic model. Technically problems in data collections for financial predictions such as the difficulty in dealing with a wide variety of data sources, the complexity and non-linearity among the relevant data collected which are not well defined by financial economic theory conduce further research on identifying predictive models in which many are subject to over-fitting and poor predictive out-of-sample performance. What is really needed is a model that can learn such complex data input features and leads to better predictions of the target output variables (portfolio return, optimal portfolio structure) (Heaton, Polson and Witte, 2016). This thesis proposed a novelty method using machine learning namely deep learning for portfolio optimization. The proposed model consists of two networks. The first network works for stock returns prediction, ranking and selection of top performing ones. The second network is to find the optimal set of portfolio weights for portfolio optimization.

3.2. Machine Learning Techniques

Machine learning (ML) can be explained as the use of data to train a certain model and use the trained model to make predictions from new data. ML techniques are useful for financial prediction and classification problems (Heaton, Polson and Witte, 2016).

The study by (Yang, Liu and Wu, 2018) employs established machine learning algorithms namely linear regression, ridge regression, step wise regression, random forest and GBM for stock recommendation. The strength of ML techniques in data analysis has been demonstrated as they outperform the established S&P 500 method. The data used in the study is divided into training groups of varying duration (16 to 40 quarters) and four quarters of test data. Based on the result, a trading model is selected for the three-month trading period i.e. the train, test and trade cycle. The training test is built using top 20 financial indicators from Wharton Research Data Services (WRDS). The historical data and S&P horizon is used to predict quarter-long return. Traditionally the linear regression model is used to predict stock values. However, for increased accuracy the proposed technique (successfully) employs multiple regression estimators. Mean Square Error (MSE) is used as the performance metric. The technique picks the model with lowest MSE and uses it over the next 3-month trading period. As a final step, features are assigned coefficients (indicating importance). A ‘final table’ is prepared that comprises of selected stocks with trading predictions and portfolio allocation. Once the table is available the critical step of portfolio allocation is achieved by constraints introduced using mean-variance and minimum-variance. The empirical results are compared against the benchmark equal-weight portfolio technique. All three outperform the S&P 500 in terms of Sharpe ratio on both 12-year sample data (1995-2007) and overall performance. The overall Sharpe ratio for minimum-variance is highest at 0.462 and only 0.195 for S&P 500. However, as stock trading generates huge data it would be interesting to see the comparison between the proposed techniques and deep learning based methods. The latter is expected to outperform with big enough training set. It is worth mentioning that the highest Sharpe value is sub-optimal (less than 1).

Traditional methods for variable annuity (VA) portfolio risk management rely on nested simulations (NS). The study made by (Xu *et al.*, 2018) presents a moment matching method based on regime-switching lognormal (Hardy, 2001) that is 10x times faster but still computationally expensive. The moment matching method is combined with three machine learning (MMML) techniques namely random forest (MMRF), regression tree (MMRT) and neural network (MMNN). The input features are key VA contract attributes i.e. guarantee type, gender, age, account value, withdrawal rate, and maturity. Ten fold cross validation optimizes important parameters for each ML technique. Computational time and risk management reliability is evaluated for dollar deltas, VaRs and CVaRs. In addition to NS, the proposed technique is also evaluated against unified kriging for function data or UKFD (Gan and Lin, 2015). Only contracts with GMDB and GMWB riders have been included for experimentation. The dataset comprises of 10,000 contracts over a period of 25 years. The mean absolute error is used as performance metric.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |f_i - y_i|,$$

where f_i is the predicted value and y_i is the actual value. Similarly, the accuracy metric is the percentage absolute error (PAE) for all quantities

$$PAE = \frac{|\sum_{i=1}^n f_i - \sum_{i=1}^n y_i|}{|\sum_{i=1}^n y_i|}.$$

The experiments first consider individual contracts by generating around 50 scenarios. The results are close to NS benchmarks but 80 times faster in calculations for VaR and CVaR and 150 times faster for delta dollar. The second experiment considers a larger portfolio of 10,000 contracts with total value of more than 2 billion dollars. The NS with 1000 outer loops and 10,000 inner paths is used as benchmark. Three portfolio sizes are used for experimentation i.e. 500, 1000 and 2000. The portfolio risk management is much more accurate as the portfolio size increases. However, MMNN does require a relatively large training set. In terms of computational time the MMTR is most efficient, the NS computation requires almost 98 hours on a CPU. The UKFD is 30-40 times slower than MMTR. The presented technique is not only reliable in large portfolio risk management but also computationally efficient.

Although, the aforementioned ML techniques perform well but the performance can be further improved by more advanced deep learning (DL) based ML techniques. In the proceeding section we review methodologies that rely on the concept.

3.2.1. Deep Neural Networks

Hopfield neural network has been used by (Fernández and Gómez, 2007) for solving portfolio selection problem by developing a heuristic model. Main focus is drawing the efficient frontier for the general mean variance model with cardinality as well as bounding constraints. Restrictions such as these guarantee investment related to a specified number of various securities and restrict the size of capital invested per asset. The study was conducted on the weekly prices of five indexes (Hang Seng, DAX 100, FTS100, S&P100 and Nikkei 225) over the period March 1992-1997, and an allocation of specific number of assets was given for each index.

The study illustrated that when evaluating the Markowitz mean variance model, these constraints result in an issue related to portfolio selection with a mix of quadratic and integral programming problems for which there is no computational efficient algorithms. However, they found that the objective function in the general mean-variance model related to the portfolio selection problem bears a uniform energy function in Hopfield networks and accordingly it will be diminished if Hopfield's dynamics are followed. Lastly, the neural network model has been reviewed as being more suitable for superior solutions as compared to "other heuristic methods from the field of genetic algorithms, tabu search and simulated annealing" when seeking well diversification portfolios with low risk (Fernández and Gómez, 2007).

The study made by (Heaton, Polson and Witte, 2016) stated that traditionally, S&P 500 approximations are based on selecting only a group of stocks that either give comparable *performance* to observed index or largely represent the *aggregate information* of stocks. The former is essentially a trial and error based (linear regression) approach. A deep network readily identifies even non-linear patterns as the data is passed through adaptive linear layers. As the data is processed through these layers, new representation is learnt at each layer i.e. this is termed as deep feature policy (DFP). However, there are some serious drawbacks i) converging to trivial and ii) over fitting to aggregate data. Autoencoders remedy this situation by using 'Bottleneck' structure. This creates a compressed representation of the stock data through both linear and non-linear representations. The study then compares how closely this representation resembles the actual S&P 500 index. The top ten stocks (communal) and bottom ten stocks (individualistic) are used to create a basis representation for an autoencoder network. This is used for approximation of S&P 500 index, which can be further improved by using DFP although it requires diversity in training data. The major observation of this study is that deep networks are an effective tool for out-sample approximation quality. This is demonstrated over a four-year data (2010-2014), approximations obtained through autoencoding accurately replicate the original index. This addresses the major drawback of classic models i.e. focusing on in-sample approximation (Heaton, Polson and Witte, 2016).

The amount of data generated in stock trading makes use of deep networks ideal. But the volume and complexity of data needs to be understood. The study made by (Huck, 2019) takes a look at the use of large datasets and machine learning (ML) techniques for statistical arbitrage in context of financial data. The input features (stock indicators) are classified as Lagged Returns (LR), dummies to Identify precisely each stock (ID), Time, Industry and Risk (TIR) and Externalities (Ex). The data set sizes vary from 11 to a maximum of 592 predictors. The training set has either 50400 (100 stocks) or 151200 (300 stocks) samples. Four ML techniques (classification model) are used i.e. deep belief network (DBN), random forest (RF), DBN with dimensionality reduction and Elastic net regression (Zou and Hastie, 2005). The initial results indicate that ML models clearly outperform the market with average annualized return of 35% versus 10%, excluding transaction costs. The RF gives the best predictive performance. The results indicate that one-day forecasting works better than five. The performance deteriorates when all predictors are used, especially for DBN. Even a hybrid approach of DBN+RF does not yield marked improvement. Elastic Regression performs well when all predictors are considered.

Recent studies have highlighted particular deep network architecture has shown to outperform others i.e. Long Short Term Memory (LSTM). This is a special case of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), these networks have the ability to retain data over time.

3.2.2. Applications of LSTM Architecture

The benefit of asset pre-selection has been empirically demonstrated (Wang *et al.*, 2020) by combining Long-Short Time Memory (LSTM) deep network in combination with Markowitz's mean-variance or MV model. The proposed LSTM+MV approach uses six established indicators as input variables namely return, RSI, MoM, TR, ATR and Parabolic SAR. The 25-year (1994-2005) data from London Stock Exchange is divided into (overlapping) train-test sets. The first 750 days are used for training and 250 days for testing. The LSTM network, optimized by Adam algorithm (Kingma and Ba, 2014) is first used to predict top assets based on all the previous data in a particular period. These assets are expected to give highest return. The top k assets are then allocated portfolio using MV model for trading. In asset prediction stage, LSTM is compared with other ML techniques (SVM, RAF, DNN and ARIMA.) using four error metrics i.e. MSE, RMSE, MAPE, MAE and R^2 (coefficient of determination). LSTM outperforms other ML techniques for majority of stocks. It has lowest average error for all metrics and highest R^2 average. For optimal formation, three baseline strategies are formulated as Machine Learning (ML) + MV, MV + 1/N (assets are equally weighted) and Random (assets are randomly selected) + MV (or 1/N). Comparison is made in terms of standard deviation, mean return, Sharpe ratio and Sortino ratio i.e. all annualized. The empirical results indicate LSTM+MV outperforming regardless of portfolio size. In terms of financial performance, the proposed model gives both favorable daily and annual return. The cumulative return is also better than other baseline techniques with and without transaction cost.

Using machine learning techniques for portfolio management has some drawbacks, mainly ignoring relationship of assets and relying solely on synthetic (index) data. In order to address this, the study made by (Yun *et al.*, 2020) proposes Grouped-ETFs Model (GEM) with a joint cost function that considers absolute and relative return. The Exchange Traded Fund (ETF), unlike other funds combines multiple assets and has various advantages. Key stock indicators are used as input features with dimensionality reduction using principal component analysis (PCA). GEM is computed for in-group (highly correlated) and out-group assets (direction of asset price). The two-stage LSTM network uses the hyperbolic tangent function. In GEM, one model predicts in-group portfolios and multiplies each by weights that are determined by total-group model. A final assets portfolio consisting of weights is obtained. Important contribution of the study is *joint cost function*; focusing on different type of data. One component focuses on increase/decrease of asset price (directional) and other on relative asset profit (continuous). Training of network using cost function gives us comprehensive information regarding price fluctuations and relative profit. Standard Mean Square Error (MSE) is modified as follows to accommodate joint cost function (JC_t) as:

$$JC_t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_{t,i} - \hat{y}_{t,i})^2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (z_{t,j} - \hat{y}_{t,j})^2.$$

The first term gives us the direction as either 0 or 1. The second term gives continuous data from 0 to 1.

Machine learning techniques, including a conventional single stage in-group deep learning model are integrated with ETF (IEMs) is used as evaluation baseline. In addition to LSTM, other techniques are also used with GEM for comparison. Extensive ETF data from MSCI ACWI (Morgan Stanley Capital International (MSCI) All Country World Index (ACWI) ETFs) global portfolio is obtained for experiments. The dataset from 32 countries spans a period of 15 years i.e. 20-May-2002 to 08-Jun-2017. Using sliding window simulation, the working of actual fund is achieved. The model learns from 30-day data (rebalancing period). This continuous update of training data ensures that method performs better than uniform sampling. The 10% of the training data is used for validation. The test data consists of 1590 datasets created from 31-Jan-2013 to 08-Jun-2017. The proposed technique is compared against Integrated ETF Model (IEMs) based on four other machine learning techniques using eight metrics. GEM clearly outperforms IEMs by 15.0%. Using Sharpe ratio, performance of GEM outperforms by 27.0% on average. The GEM with LSTM performs best followed by GEM+SVM (4.6% difference). The joint cost function outperforms the baseline by 11.7%. The proposed technique also outperforms when ETFs are grouped using business sectors (Yun *et al.*, 2020).

(Holgersson, Karlsson and Stephan, 2020) had worked on the problem of determining portfolio weights that can minimize the variance of portfolio estimators. Their paper had compared the risk functions that drive the efficient portfolio weight estimators thereby focusing on the risk associated with these estimators. The risk functions included are risk functions of covariance matrix estimators, forecast mean square errors, directional risks and conditional risks. They used the concept of reducing the variance of excess returns by using global minimum variance portfolio (GMVP). The GMVP family of weight estimators included the ones suggested by [(Frahm and Memmel, 2010),(Bodnar and Zabolotsky, 2017), (Holgersson, Karlsson and Stephan, 2020)]. To investigate the efficiency of GMVP, the authors used Monte Carlo simulation using DGP I, DGP II and DGP III data generation techniques. Multiple samples were used for study from Nasdaq and Stockholm stock exchange using both fixed and random sampling methods. The overall findings of the work stated that no estimator dominates uniformly overall risk functions. However, the dominating tendencies can be established based on the usage of different estimators. The estimator proposed by (Frahm and Memmel, 2010) was found to perform better than the one proposed by (Bodnar and Zabolotsky, 2017) under certain conditions. The research was however silent on the hypothesis testing and other general inferential aspects.

The study made by (Aboussalah and Lee, 2020) presents Stacked Deep Dynamic Recurrent Reinforcement Learning (SDDRRL) that stacks traditional RRL structures. It considers temporal dependency i.e. new market conditions are given importance and only recent decisions are optimized. A single trade/test round has 1200 hours of training and 300 hours of testing. Such twenty rounds are put through SDDRRL. The data is of 7928 hour duration (01-Jan-2013 to 01-Jul-2017) collected from ten different S&P 500 sectors. Bayesian optimization of hyper-parameters by Gaussian Process (GP) is used to search best architecture. The objective is to find global optimum in minimum iterations. Initialization is done by 25 randomized iterations and then 150 iterations of GP optimizations. Evaluation results are obtained over a 3.5 years horizon. Five SDDLRL architectures are used in evaluation and are compared with three alternate trading strategies i.e. mean-variance optimization (MVO), risk parity model and UBAH index. Best SDDLRL architecture gives a return of 94.71% at iteration #200, while UBAH performs best amongst the benchmarks with 39.8%. The hour glass architecture (resembling auto-encoder) seems to be best suited for this type of application; the underlying reason however needs to be investigated.

A study compares (Siami-Namini and Namin, 2018) LSTM architecture with Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average or ARIMA (Mishkin and Eakins, 2015) is an established technique that builds a composite model:

$$x_t = c + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i x_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t + \sum_{i=0}^q \theta_i \varepsilon_{t-i}$$

The first term is the Autoregressive (AR) model (order p) and second term is the Moving Average (MA) model (order q). The ϕ_i gives correlation coefficients and ε_t is the Gaussian white noise with variance σ^2 . The ARIMA has an order of (p,d,q) . The introduction of d makes the model stationary i.e. difference of observations obtained at different time. The LSTM is a special case of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN).

The data from previous steps is saved (*memory line*) to predict future trends making it ideal for use in applications involving financial data. The experiments focus on two research questions, i) which algorithm is more accurate for time series data and ii) does the number of epochs affect model accuracy? The stock market data for experiments spanned from January 1985 to August 2018 was extracted from Yahoo Finance website. Economics time series data was extracted from Federal Reserve Bank and IMF websites. The data is extensive e.g. for transportation (TR) commodity the data spans from Jan 1947 to July 2017. Both types of data were split into training (70%) and test (30%) subsets. Experiments use a mechanism called *Rolling Forecasting Origin* (Hyndman, 2014) i.e. focusing on the immediate next forecast. The experimental results clearly indicate the Rolling LSTM is much accurate. There is a reduction of 87% and 84% in error (RMSE) for financial and economic data respectively. The authors conclude that more than one training epoch would not have a considerable impact on accuracy. In our opinion this might not be true for all datasets. Also, optimal tuning of hyper-parameters cannot be achieved in a single epoch. The study further establishes the strength of LSTM deep architecture.

4. Conclusions

The series of development that have been made to the portfolio theory, the mean variance portfolio theory developed by Markowitz remains the cornerstone of the modern portfolio theory. However, the formulation of the Markowitz model does not take into consideration the unexpected increase in portfolio value as well as the inability to eliminate the market or systematic risk with an efficient portfolio (Hadi, El Nagggar and Abdel Bary, 2016). From a technical point of view, portfolio selection problem takes into consideration several real-world constraints such as trade limits, portfolio size, cardinality and bounding constraints. These problems found their way for obtaining better solutions using new models particularly the artificial neural networks which in turn provides insights for future research to clarify reality better.

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